

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

INTERMEDIARY REPORT

on dissemination and communication activities

Deliverable 5.2

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Executive Summary

This report introduces and assesses the AGEMERA project's communication and dissemination (COMDISS) activities and their success in the first half of the project.

In AGEMERA, COMDISS activities are carried out and monitored under WP5, led by GEO. The objectives of communication and dissemination in AGEMERA have been to:

- Promote the project's mission through various communication activities and channels and to a wide audience and maximise visibility;
- Convey the project results to a variety of stakeholders, end-users and key actors;
- Exchange knowledge and foster collaboration with other projects and initiatives which align with our project's objectives and focus on similar challenges.

All COMDISS activities have been supported by the consortium members in the various EU Member States and Zambia. Partners supported and carried out these activities using the materials produced in WP5, promoting the project in the international, national, and local events they participated in.

COMDISS activities put emphasis on reaching out to the various target groups identified, creating meaningful engagement. In the period M1-18, COMDISS activities focussed on general awareness raising regarding the project objectives and building a community where foreseen project results could reach targeted audiences as it was set out in D5.1:

- **Year 1: Raising awareness**
 - This will be achieved by building on the internal knowledge and contacts of the consortium and creating joint campaigns with existing networks. The purpose of this phase is to shed light on a much-debated topic.
- **Year 2: Building a community**
 - Workshops and events will help to bring AGEMERA to a narrower and more targeted audience. The aim is to start building expectations towards AGEMERA results.
- **Year 3: Conveying results**
 - Going into the third year, the project results will start to materialise, and they will be widely disseminated across all channels and relevant platforms.

COMDISS activities have been continuously tracked and kept recorded in dedicated online tables. Partners have been regularly reporting on their activities with the required details. The activities were planned ahead and also discussed regularly in WP5 meetings.

This document analyses the impacts of the COMDISS activities conducted during M1-18, with special attention to:

- Communications channels and activities;
- Dissemination materials;
- Publications;
- Peer-to-peer exchanges;
- Key Performance Indicators of COMDISS activities.

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1. Assessing the impact of communication activities

1.1 Communication channels

Channels for communication and dissemination were set up at the beginning of the project with the following aims and principles:

- Messages tailored to the targeted audiences
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Ability to exploit synergies
- Openness – sharing openly all non-sensitive project results as widely as possible

The utilisation of these channels aims to ensure a high level of exploitation of the project's potential, creating an impact on as many groups as possible.

1.1.1 Project website

The [AGEMERA website](#) was launched within the first months of the project, and it has been regularly updated to reflect the activities of the project and share news related to the project's progress and achievements, serving as the focal point of all communication on AGEMERA. The structure of the website was built following a thorough analysis of the project objectives and envisioned activities, as well as the common UX (User Experience) rules. Its design reflects the distinctive visual identity that was developed specifically for the project. The website incorporates different sections:

- **Who We Are**, where the key information related to the project's background, objectives, partners and advisory board, and related initiatives is stored
- **Our Work**, where the twofold overarching aim of the project is introduced to the audience: innovative mineral exploration through the use of novel and non-invasive technologies and tools and raising awareness of the importance of critical raw materials and the need for a sustainable supply of such materials to fuel the twin transition
- **Tools and Resources**, where the public deliverables (reports) produced in the project are stored to enhance the visibility of AGEMERA's outputs
- **Media**, which is further divided into two sections, one dedicated to a Media Kit including a project summary and the communication materials produced in the project for further use by media outlets aiming to share information about AGEMERA, and the other one listing the news and blogs that showcase project developments, events the partners have taken place in, scientific publications, field trips and internal meetings within the consortium

- **Contact Us**, where users can address their questions and concerns directly to the AGEMERA team by filling in a short form

The website also integrates links to the project's social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter) to make it easier for users to access them, as well as a newsletter subscription form.

The design and implementation of a [new webpage](#) was led by GEO in cooperation with TUBAF to promote the university courses that would be launched under Task 2.3. The webpage introduces the courses and their thematic focus, provides application guidelines for prospective students, lists the universities involved, and highlights the unique selling points of the courses to foster a high number of applicants.

University Courses

By 2050, through its ambitious Green Deal strategy, the EU has set out to achieve climate neutrality by transitioning to a more modern, sustainable, and resilient economy. This will not be possible without a steady and secure supply of the so-called **critical raw materials (CRMs)**: metals and minerals that are vital across multiple industries.

The **AGEMERA university courses** focus on the impact of CRMs in relation with the green and digital transition. Furthermore, the courses aim to help students in understanding the whole value chain of CRMs concerning sustainable production within Europe.

Thematic focus

Rare earth elements (REEs)

Battery raw materials (BRMs)

To monitor **website engagement**, GEO uses the reports provided by Google Analytics. According to these reports, AGEMERA's website attracted a total of **2,100 visitors**, out of which 1,900 were unique visitors. Based on previous experience, the numbers are expected to increase considerably towards the end of the project, when the project outcomes and results will be showcased on the website.

Google Analytics reports also provide information regarding the country of the users, the number of times each page was accessed, and user trajectory. According to these, the vast majority of users come from countries such as Finland, Spain, and Poland. These countries are also represented in the consortium and are part of the selected areas for the project field studies. Most users arrive at the website either directly or through organic search, and the most popular pages are the homepage, the Partners page, and the Our Story page. This clearly indicates an interest in the project goals, background, and consortium (which is made up of reputable academic and industry members).

The AGEMERA project website was also listed as a nominee in the **.eu Web Awards** competition, which acknowledges the most visually appealing and compelling websites with the .eu domain. This was an excellent opportunity to increase the project's visibility among new audiences. A social media campaign was launched to encourage followers to vote for AGEMERA in the competition.

1.1.2 Communication on partner websites

All AGEMERA partners are committed to increase the project's visibility and share news and updates regarding its objectives and milestones. A first step in their communication efforts has been to announce the project launch and present key information about it on their own websites, thus ensuring a higher outreach. These efforts can be seen in the selection of screenshots below and are complemented by social media communication.

AGEMERA

PROJECTS ONGOING PROJECTS

AGEMERA – Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials

Europe's goals in green and digital transition require innovative methods, techniques, and technologies to be used in mineral exploration. Europe has long traditions in base metal mining but has been less successful in developing projects to source CRMs whether lack of investments, the diverse national permitting procedures and the low levels of the public acceptance.

AGEMERA is a three-year research project that focuses on securing the European supply and independence of critical raw materials (CRMs) in order to meet the objectives of the green transition. CRMs are the key for the

PROJECT INFO

Coordinator: University of Oulu
 Years: 2022-2025
 Official website
 Funding

AGEMERA
 Agile Exploration and Geo-modelling for European Critical Raw materials

New environmental, economic and societal requirements in the EU's transition to a low-carbon and digital economy call for innovative methods, technologies and techniques to be developed and applied in mineral exploration. As global demand for critical raw materials (CRM) continues to grow rapidly, mobilizing Europe's domestic potential is an essential part of the EU becoming more resilient and developing open strategic autonomy. To unlock the potentials of CRM in Europe, AGEMERA conducts local state-of-art geological and geophysical surveys over a total of ~4,700 km² in order to detailly map CRM resources in 6 EU countries and 1 third country (Zambia). The geophysical field trial surveys will demonstrate three novel non-invasive survey methods based on remote sensing and related data analysis: 1) passive seismic methods, 2) multi-sensing drone system combining magnetic, radiometric and electromagnetic sensing, and 3) muon-based multidetector density detection system. The project will use data from open-access databases (e.g., European Geological Data Infrastructure, EGDl), the data collected from the field by project geoscientists, and various geophysical survey methods to refine and improve the genetic mineral system models of the various deposit types known to contain lithium, cobalt, molybdenum, vanadium, niobium, tantalum, bauxite and REE. The project will survey citizens in the project countries, create a CRM educational package targeting schools and universities, publish an online CRM serious game, organize public events, as well as online news flashes, with the aim to reach 5,000,000 citizens by 2030. The project will create an open-access SoftGIS analysis and database on people's social, cultural, environmental and economic concerns related to mining and mineral exploration. These data enable the creation of socio-economic potential maps to be used in parallel with the geological potential maps, consequently ensuring a basis for socially accepted and sustainable mining.

Start date	2022-08-01
End date	2025-07-31
Budget	€7,494,660
Funding programme	Horizon Europe
Website	https://agemera.eu/

1.1.3 Newsletter

To further engage with the public and build a community around the project, the [AGEMERA newsletter](#) was created. Two newsletter issues have been sent out by January 2024, at an interval of 5 months, featuring the project's key achievements and milestones, the field trips organised as part of AGEMERA's work in gathering data and testing its novel technologies, events the consortium took part in, as well as upcoming events.

The website features a subscription form in the footer section where website users can sign up to receive the newsletter, should they want to learn more about the project. To boost the number of subscribers, a social media campaign was launched, with the AGEMERA consortium joining in and resharing the posts across their own networks. As of January 2024, the AGEMERA newsletter has 35 subscribers.

1.1.4 Social media channels

Four social media accounts have been created to support AGEMERA's dissemination and communication goals, share news about the project and its activities, engage with stakeholders, including the general public, and foster a sense of community around the project. These four channels are LinkedIn, X (previously Twitter), Facebook and YouTube. The selection of the appropriate channels was made by GEO upon consultation with partners and taking into account the project objectives and target audiences.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a social platform that allows professionals to search and apply for jobs and network with other professionals in their own fields and beyond. Through its nature, LinkedIn boasts a more formal style of communication and fosters the creation of genuine communities among certain topics, areas of study, or fields. AGEMERA's [LinkedIn profile](#) has been the project's most successful channel to date, cumulating 428 followers.

X (previously Twitter)

X (formerly known as Twitter) is a social platform that uses short messages to convey information, with a limit of 280 characters per post. A popular feature of X is the hashtags, which are placed in front of specific keywords, making it easy for the user to search for information related to a specific topic. [AGEMERA's Twitter account](#) has been featuring information related to the project goals and its work, but has been used specifically and extensively during internal meetings and external events (such as the EU SuperCluster Geoconference Lapland) for live coverage (multiple posts outlining the key takeaways from these events). AGEMERA's X account has cumulated 156 followers.

Facebook

Despite the fact that its popularity has decreased in recent years, Facebook is still widely used in some countries, including the countries that are part of AGEMERA's focus. To this end, [AGEMERA's Facebook profile](#) has been used to raise awareness of the project's aim and the importance of critical raw materials, share updates and news related to the project activities, and promote the partners' participation in prestigious events on an international and national level. AGEMERA's Facebook page currently has 49 followers.

YouTube

YouTube is the most popular platform for online video sharing worldwide, featuring various types of content, from music and news to documentaries and other educational videos. The [AGEMERA YouTube profile](#) has been launched to promote the videos produced in the project and share interviews with partners and external stakeholders, as well as short clips showcasing the novel technologies the project makes use of. For the moment, it features two videos: an interview with the project coordinator, and AGEMERA's introductory video that explains the challenges the project addresses and the routes it aims to take to achieve its goals.

Social Media Campaigns

By M18, two social media campaigns have been launched to boost the project's visibility and reach new audiences. The first campaign was dedicated to promoting the project partners: a post was created to showcase each consortium member and shed light on their expertise and the role they fulfil in AGEMERA. The second campaign was launched under the hashtag #AGEMERAexplains with the purpose of explaining the concept notions and concepts AGEMERA operates with to non-specialist audiences in a clear and digestible way. This is linked to the project's objective of raising awareness of the importance of critical raw materials and their role in advancing green and digital transitions. A few examples can be seen below.

1.1.5 Partner social media channels

The AGEMERA consortium is very active in contributing to the project's communication efforts by resharing or liking posts and engaging with the content that is published on the main channels. In turn, this helps boost the visibility of the project and, ultimately, the number of followers as the partners leverage their networks to increase AGEMERA's outreach capacity.

1.1.6 Videos

The first [AGEMERA project video](#) was created within the first year of the project. GEO led its production. A first version of the project video was shown to the consortium during the second GA meeting for feedback and suggestions on how to further improve the video to reflect the project's message and convey its objectives in the best way possible. A second and final version of the video was released and published on the project's YouTube channel, but also organically on LinkedIn and Facebook, as this has been proven to increase engagement.

The video follows the "project-solution" approach, detailing the challenges we are facing (a shortage of domestic critical raw materials coupled with reliance on third countries to supply these materials) and the ways AGEMERA sets to tackle the challenges (new areas for exploration, using innovative and environmentally friendly tools, developing educational packages). It has gathered more than 700 views across all channels, and it includes subtitles to improve accessibility and ensure an inclusive approach.

Another [short video](#) was produced at the kick-off meeting of the project that took place in Oulu, Finland, and it consists of a short interview with Jari Joutsenvaara, AGEMERA's coordinator, on the topic of critical raw materials and the vital role they play in our modern life. Until M36, several other videos are envisioned to showcase the novel technologies AGEMERA's industry partners have developed or deployed in the project.

1.1.7 Dissemination and communication materials

In the first 18 months of the project, various dissemination and communication materials were designed and produced, tailored to specific purposes, which included sharing general information about the project and the technologies developed and tested in AGEMERA. These materials followed the distinctive visual identity developed by GEO for the project and included:

- A set of templates for both internal and external use (Word, Excel, PowerPoint)
- Two flyers (in A5 and A6 format)
- A project roll-up
- Three project posters

Flyers

A four-sided flyer was produced at the beginning of the project for general promotion purposes. It includes key information about the project (mission, partners, and objectives), and it features a **QR code** that leads to the project website and social media handles to boost visibility. The original version of this flyer was created in English, with 3 additional flyers being produced in some of the **partners' local languages (German, Finnish, Croatian)** to increase the project's outreach among local communities. The flyer was sent out to partners with the printing margins in place to encourage them to print it locally – a more environmentally friendly approach.

A second flyer was produced for the ZIMEC event AGEMERA's partner Radai took part in Zambia. This flyer centres around the innovative tools and technologies used in the project (drone-based surveys, muon-density surveys, and passive seismic methods).

Roll-up

A roll-up was designed and produced for partners to use when organising or participating in events. The roll-up includes the key information about the project's mission and partners, a QR code that leads to the project website, and the social media handles to boost following.

Posters

A promotional poster for the project was created at the beginning, including information about AGEMERA's mission and partners, as well as the social media handles to boost following.

Two more posters were created afterwards for specific purposes. The first one features a project description and the current status of its work, and it was included in the poster exhibition that was organised during the EU SuperCluster

Geoconference Lapland on 30-31 October 2023. The second one was created for the EU Raw Materials Week to promote the launch of the AGEMERA university course, which is due in spring 2024.

Critical raw materials' role in the green and digital transitions

AGEMERA launches university courses to raise awareness of how critical raw materials (CRMs) impact our everyday lives and the significance they have for the EU's Green Deal ambitions

Focus

The courses will address issues related to critical raw materials, particularly:

Rare earth elements (REEs)

and

Battery raw materials (BRMs)

And how they:

- Contribute to our modern, highly technologized lifestyles
- Are a key element of the green and digital transition objectives
- Impact the geopolitical and economic landscape
 - Can give birth to social and environmental concerns – and what to do about it
 - Are related to the UNFC (UN Framework for Classification of Resources) and UNRMS (UN Resource Management System) frameworks

Benefits for students:

- ★ flexible learning: online and remote
- ★ access to literature and resources to support individual learning
- ★ live discussions with tutors
- ★ prominent guest speakers from reputable institutions in the field
- ★ certificate of attendance
- ★ ECTS credits upon successful completion

Universities involved

Platform

The courses will take place on **Opal - Bildungsportal Sachsen (TU Bergakademie Freiberg)**

Lecturing period

the gap between the winter 2023/2024 and the summer 2024 semesters

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ENROLLMENT
WILL BEGIN SOON

1.2 Publications

During the first half of the project, ten peer-reviewed open-access articles were published by AGEMERA partners (see Table 1 below).

Table 1. List of peer-reviewed scientific publications in the first half of the project

Title	Date	Autor/ others involved	PID or Link	Peer-reviewed	Open access
Combining agile exploration methods with mineral chemistry for better geo-modelling of critical raw materials in Assarel porphyry copper deposit	2022 Sep	Peytcheva, I., Hikov, A. Georgiev, S., Stefanova, E. Dimitrova, D. Ivanov, D. Stoilov, V. Vasilev, I. Holma, M.	https://www.geologica-balkanica.eu/abstract-books	Yes	Yes
Assessing the potential of Assarel porphyry copper deposit for critical raw materials: mineral-geochemical data for combination with agile exploration methods and better geo-modeling	2022 Dec	Peytcheva, I., Hikov, A. Georgiev, S., Stefanova, E. Dimitrova, D. Ivanov, D. Stoilov, V. Vasilev, I. Holma, M.	https://doi.org/10.52215/rev.bgs.2022.83.3.113	yes	yes
Agile Exploration and Geo-modelling for European Critical Raw Materials – Introduction to the AGEMERA project	2022 Nov	"M. Holma, J. Kortenieni, G. Casini, E. Saura, F. Šumanovac, J. Kapuralić and F. Tornos"	https://www.seismo.helsinki.fi/ilp/lito2022/Lithosphere_2022_Symposium_Abstract_Volume.pdf	Yes	Yes
Applications of cosmic-ray muon imaging in Earth Sciences	2023 Mar	Holma, M.	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369304721_Applications_of_cosmic-ray_muon_imaging_in_Earth_Sciences	Yes	Yes
Horizon Europe project AGEMERA: Combining novel methodologies for agile exploration and geomodelling of critical raw materials deposits	2023 Mar	Holma, M., Peytcheva, I., Šumanovac, I., Tornos, F. Nyambe, I., Joutsenvaara, J.	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369305265_Horizon_Europe_project_AGEMERA_Combining_novel_methodologies_for_agile_exploration_and_geomodelling_of_critical_raw_materials_deposits	Yes	Yes
Using a new geophysical tool for improving underground safety in mining and civil engineering: time-sequential muography	2023 Apr	Holma, M., Kortenieni, J., Kuusiniemi, P. & Zhang, Z.-X.	https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU23/EGU23-3567.html	Yes	Yes
Numerical and Analytical Determination of Rockburst	2023 Oct	Witold Pytel, Krzysztof Fuławka, Bogumiła	https://doi.org/10.3390/app132111881	Yes	Yes

Characteristics: Case Study from Polish Deep Copper Mine		Pałac-Walko, Piotr Mertuszka			
AGEMERA: FUELLING A GREENER ECONOMY VIA INNOVATIVE MINERAL EXPLORATION	2023 Oct	Holma, M.	https://tupa.gtk.fi/raportti/arkisto/55_2023.pdf	Yes	yes
AGEMERA project studies local people's perceptions: is the mineral industry supporting the future of local communities?	2023 Oct	Leena Suopajärvi, Mari Tulilehto	https://tupa.gtk.fi/raportti/arkisto/55_2023.pdf	yes	yes
Horizon Europe Project AGEMERA	2023 Oct	Jari Joutsenvaara, Marko Holma, Georg Meissner, Taras Matselyukh, Francisco Gutierrez and Leena Suopajärvi	https://tupa.gtk.fi/raportti/arkisto/55_2023.pdf	yes	yes
Modelling Cover- Collapse Sinkholes that Appeared after the M6.2 Petrinja Earthquake in Croatia Using Electrical Resistivity Tomography Data	2023	Šumanovac, F.; Pekaš, Ž.	https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021124	yes	yes

1.3 Peer-to-peer exchanges

Partners were active in participating in (or organising) various events where interactions and synergies were formed. These interactions and presentations of AGEMERA objectives and ongoing results were ongoing through the period M1-18, involving various peer groups, like science, industry, or policy. Such interactions took place mainly through different kinds of events.

1.3.1 Participation at conferences

AGEMERA partners actively participated in conferences and engaged with the scientific community (listed below). Participation took the forms of presentations, conference papers, and posters related to methods or activities in AGEMERA. The EU SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference needs to be highlighted here, being a major event co-organised by AGEMERA and sister projects, providing meaningful cooperation potentials on the scientific and business levels.

- SDIMI (Sustainable Development in the Minerals Industry) 10th International Conference, Namibia, 2022
- 65th International Scientific Conference; University of Mining and Geology, Bulgaria, 2022
- 1st European Conference on Teaching and Research in Sustainable Resource Extraction, Germany, 2023

- XXII International Congress of the Carpathian-Balkan Geological Association (CBGA), Bulgaria, 2022
- 12th Symposium on the Structure, Composition, and Evolution of the Lithosphere, Finland
- Sustainable Resource Society; Finland. 2022
- MINEXCHANGE 2023 SME Annual Conference & Expo, USA
- 1st GeoDays; Finland, 2023
- NAEPEC Africa & Mediterranean Energy & Hydrogen Exhibition and Conference), Barcelona, 2023
- 2nd International Conference on Raw Materials and Circular Economy, Greece, 2023
- 54th International October Conference on Mining and Metallurgy, Serbia, 2023
- SEG 2023 Conference: Resourcing the Green Transition, England, 2023
- XXXIII School of Underground Mining, Poland, 2023
- XLIV Winter School of Rock Mechanics and Geoengineering, Poland, 2023
- EIT Raw Materials Week; Belgium, 2022 and 2023,
- 7th Croatian Geological Congress, Croatia, 2023
- GEOSCIENCES 2023 Conference, Bulgaria, 2023
- ZIMEC Mining Conference, Zambia, 2023
- FEM Fennoscandian Mining and Exploration, Finland, 2023
- EU SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference, Finland, 2023

1.3.2 Seminars or workshops organised/participated in

The facilitation of face-to-face activities with stakeholder groups or the general public was initiated only from M15, as project results have started to be characterised/produced. The University of Oulu and the University of Lapland organised two open seminars for the local general public about the results of the questionnaire (Deliverable 2.1). The outreach of the events had limited success in terms of the size of the audiences. The experience was assessed and considered carefully for the planning and design of future events (upcoming workshops).

1.3.3 Collaboration with sister projects and in cluster events

During the first half of the project, AGEMERA established a range of connections with relevant initiatives under EU-funded or other initiatives to help maximise outreach. Partners were active in identifying and exploiting possibilities for cooperation, which resulted in numerous activities and potential synergies.

Numerous cooperation activities were carried out with AGEMERA sister projects EIS, AGEMERA, CIRAN, EXCEED, GOLDENEYE, GREENPEG, M4MINING, MaDiTraCe, MinExTarget, MultiMiner, S34I, SEEMS DEEP and SEMACRET. The EU SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference stands out of activities. It was co-organised by AGEMERA and was one of the main networking events in this period. These clustering and networking events are detailed further in **Deliverable 5.4** (Intermediary report on synergies and collaboration).

2. Key Performance Indicators related to communication and dissemination

Originally, 10 key performance indicators were defined, which were later revisited and refined in Deliverable 5.1 (Dissemination and communication plan and visual identity). As refinements occurred, the KPIs are introduced here based on the currently valid Dissemination and Communication Plan. These are listed in Table 2, along with their set targets for M6 and M24 (as the closest points to M18), as well as the numbers achieved numbers in this period.

Table 2. Progress towards KPIs in AGEMERA during M1-18

KPIs	M6	M24 (cumulative)	Achieved by M18
Social media campaign – Twitter (visitors)	(Total cumulative for M36) – 1000		156 followers
Social media campaign – LinkedIn (members)	(Total cumulative for M36) – 2000		428 followers on LinkedIn
Project video	1	2	1 video - 735 views (LinkedIn+YouTube)
Press releases	1	3	1
Posters	1	4	8
Publications (peer-reviewed)	1	4	10
Articles	3	15	4 media articles
CRM Educational Package (visitors)	-	1000	-
CRM Serious Game (sessions)	-	-	-
Workshops	-	-	-

Further details, such as the type and number of communication and dissemination activities completed in each of the KPI tracks, will be presented in detail in the Periodic Report.

Table 3. Number of communication and dissemination activities performed during M1-18

Category	Number of activities
Presentations at conferences	13
Posters at conferences	8
Participation in activities organised jointly with EU initiatives	1
Participation in other events i.e. meeting, consultation, interview	3
Organisation of seminars or workshops	2
Publications - scientific	13
Publications – non-scientific	9
Website news items	25
Audiovisual materials	2

3. Conclusions

The COMMDISS activities in AGEMERA started fast, with already tangible achievements in the first 18 months of the project, as summarised in this report. This includes a good outreach level as well as strong engagement with the project's target groups. This is reflected in the events in which the partners have participated or organised, reaching out to the members of the scientific, business, or policy communities. The project is on track towards achieving its KPIs, both in scientific dissemination and in terms of public outreach.

As the project results will be delivered more intensely in the upcoming phase of the project, we expect the engagement and outreach to increase, which means that the target groups can be targeted more effectively further. Monitoring and assessment will also be continuous through internal reporting in the upcoming period.

<https://agemera.eu/>

https://twitter.com/agemera_eu

<https://www.facebook.com/agemeraproject>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/agemeraproject/>

